

Project CHANGES - Spoke 4

Report – Stakeholder Analysis – v. 1.0

31 July 2024

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Fondazione CHANGES – Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society

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5	Engineering	ENG	Member
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10	Università degli Studi di Torino	UNITO	Member

Executive Summary

The current report is produced under the WP5 of the Spoke 4.

The report presents the methods and tools identified and prepared by the project to achieve three main goals:

- Identify and involve a number of relevant stakeholders' categories in the project activities, according to the quadruple helix engagement approach;
- Identify and implement a series of exploitation activities to disseminate the results of the project in scientific communities, through conferences and events;
- Design and develop a set of communication tools and materials to reach the targeted audience and maximise the visibility of the project and its outputs.

A list of KPIs and expected results are eventually presented in the document to measure the effectiveness of the defined actions and tools.

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1. Introduction

This report involves carrying out activities aimed at both developing appropriate communication strategies to disseminate Spoke 4 results and enhance their impact on the scientific and civic community.

To pursue these purposes, this report provides:

- Stakeholder identification and clustering, based on their interests and impact with respect to the project's issues and objectives;
- Role's definition of each stakeholder category related to project outcomes;
- the use of KPIs for measuring the levels and results of stakeholder engagement activities in the project.

To structure an appropriate strategy for achieving these goals, Suor Orsola Benincasa University (UNISOB), as the WP leader, conceived and implemented a workshop titled "CultureInDialogue."

This report aims to outline all the activities conducted as part of the workshop and, based on the outcomes of the collaborative efforts during the workshop, provide a comprehensive overview of the key stakeholder mapping and engagement strategy.

2. Goals

The “CultureInDialogue” workshop was designed in alignment with the objectives of WP5 to develop an interactive model for analyzing and mapping key stakeholders in the cultural heritage sector, identifying the best engagement strategies to promote the activities and technologies developed under the CHANGES project.

The workshop model enabled close interaction with members identified by each Spoke 4 participating organization by sharing the process of mapping key stakeholders and stakeholder networks, as well as the most effective ways to engage them.

3. Methodology

The workshop, based on the "quadruple helix" model—a well-established paradigm for fostering innovation in the knowledge sector by promoting cooperation among Government, Industry, Academia, and Civil Society—achieved the following objectives:

Stakeholder issue-mapping

- Identify a set of key stakeholders pertaining to the cultural heritage sector and their networks in industrial, academic, institutional and civil society contexts;
- Cluster the identified stakeholders or stakeholder networks based on their specific interests and expertise related to the Cultural Heritage theme and Spoke 4 activities.

Stakeholder influence-mapping

- Evaluate the impact of mapped stakeholder engagement based on their influence in the context of Cultural Heritage to identify a strategy functional to the goals of Spoke 4.

Stakeholder involvement and engagement strategy

- Check the state of the art of the degree of involvement of the identified stakeholder relative to Spoke 4 activities;
- Define one or more engagement strategies for each identified stakeholder or network of stakeholders.

FIGURE 1 METHODOLOGICAL OBJECTIVES

To assess the effectiveness and impact of engagement, enhancement and communication activities, two key performance indicators (KPIs) for “Stakeholder Involvement” were identified:

1. the involvement of at least 10-15 stakeholders in Spoke 4;
2. the identification of at least one relevant professional network.

This initiative represents a crucial preliminary stage for initiating further processes aimed at developing and consolidating collaborative relationships among the various parties involved, particularly facilitating the transfer of expertise between the research and industrial sectors. A specific methodology has been adopted to meet the objectives outlined in the report. The approach combines the use of the workshop method (which allows for direct and collaborative

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interaction among participants, facilitating the sharing of knowledge, experiences and perspectives) with the Quadruple Helix model.

In particular, the following methods were implemented to ensure an optimal process of co-creation of strategies:

- Conducting the workshop virtually to ensure maximum participation from partners;
- Using virtual platforms for the collection of preliminary data functional for the participatory phases of the workshop (Google Modules);
- Using the MIRO visual co-design platform made it possible to work simultaneously by leveraging tools and templates to build the infrastructure needed to carry out the workshop phases, optimizing processes without compromising the quality of the analysis, and indeed adding value on the methodological level and the results achieved¹.

The Quadruple Helix model—comprising Public Institutions, Industry, Civil Society, and the Research Community—promotes innovation and collaboration with a citizen/end-user-centered perspective. This model involves the active contribution of users to generate innovation. It is a well-established framework of social dynamics that relies on the networking and cooperation of diverse social sectors. The underlying principle is that innovation results from an interactive process among the four stakeholder groups—University, Industry, Government, and Civil Society—each participating based on its unique institutional function in society.

¹ For background: Li, Qingchuan et al. “How online shared whiteboarding supports online collaborative design activities: A social interaction perspective.” International Conference on Applied Human Factors and Ergonomics (2021).

QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL

FIGURE 2 QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL

This subdivision reflects the legal nature of the stakeholders identified.

The Government segment identifies stakeholders pertaining to public institutions, thus responsible for the regulatory frameworks within which development and management policies are implemented. This category includes Public Administrations, Ministries, Regions, Municipalities, Local Authorities, etc.

Industry includes companies and enterprises interested in a given activity or project, while Academy unites Universities, Research Centers, Laboratories, Living Labs, even with specific internal articulations (e.g., Departments, Institutes, etc.).

Finally, Civil Society recognizes all those territorial realities that channel actions, goals and interests of groups of citizens (e.g., associations, foundations, nonprofits, cultural and media audiences) as well as all those realities involved in producing and promoting art, research and cultural innovation outside institutional networks.

The combined use of the workshop method and the Quadruple Helix model allows for a thorough understanding of the stakeholder landscape, identifying who they are, what their interests are, and how they can be effectively involved in the project.

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4. The workshop “*CulturalInDialogo*”

The following paragraphs will explain the structure of the workshop, the distribution of participants, the preliminary preparation phase, the three main phases of the workshop, and the results obtained in each phase. The structure of the workshop was designed to maximize the interaction and participation of Spoke 4 members. The results obtained in each phase were shared and evaluated to ensure continuous feedback and progressive improvement of the decision-making process.

4.1 Structure description

Before the workshop, a preliminary questionnaire was distributed and completed by participants. This allowed to engage participants in identifying an initial group of stakeholders, dividing them into the segments of the quadruple helix.

1. The workshop was conducted virtually via Google Meet on April 18th, 2024, from 9:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m. It followed an organizational structure comprising three macro-phases, each aimed at achieving specific objectives: **Step 1 - Analysis and mapping of stakeholder interests and powers:** this phase aimed at identifying the interests and influence of various stakeholders in each segment of the quadruple helix.
2. **Step 2 - Analysis of the degree of information about the activities of Spoke 4:** This step allowed at identifying the level of familiarity of the stakeholders identified in Step 1 with the activities of CHANGES Spoke 4.
3. **Step 3 - Discussion and identification of an engagement strategy:** This final step permit the discussion of the most appropriate engagement tools and techniques to effectively engage each stakeholder.

The workshop agenda included an activities' preliminary introduction in the plenary session with institutional greetings. Afterwards, participants were divided into four discussion groups (each dedicated to one of the segments of the quadruple helix) for the first phase.

When the activity concluded, participants were again invited to plenary session for sharing the results and discuss them. The groups' opinions were summarized and shared by showing the matrices constructed for each segment of the helix. Following this phase, all participants were asked to identify, for each shared matrix, the degree to which the identified stakeholders were informed about the activities carried out by Spoke 4.

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In the third and final phase, a plenary session was led by a moderator, focusing on identifying engagement tools and techniques tailored to each stakeholder.

4.2 Participants

WP leaders, case-core leaders, and representatives from each Research Unit (RU) involved in Spoke 4 were invited to participate in the workshop. This helped to address the need to establish a shared and balanced mapping process.

Memberships were gathered using an Excel file shared with the Spoke 4 address book, which required registration including first name, last name, affiliation, email address, and role within Spoke 4. The total number of participants was No. 27, pertaining to almost all the RUs involved (UNIBO, UNISOB, UNITO, Egyptian Museum, CNR, UNIBA, UNIFI, UNIFE, ENG).

To promote active participation, we adopted a phased approach, transitioning from a "micro" level to a "macro" level of analysis. Participants were preliminarily engaged on an individual basis for initial data collection to obtain an overview of the stakeholders most relevant to the project objectives. The division into four groups facilitated in-depth discussion during the workshop regarding interests, opportunities, and potential risks or conflicts in the involvement of stakeholders identified in the preliminary phase.

The presence of moderators experienced in both European and national project management, as well as participatory team management methodologies, and with established relationships with key players in the quadruple helix, ensured that the discussions were aligned consistently with the stated objectives.

4.3 Preliminary phase

The preliminary phase consisted in the distribution of a questionnaire via Google Forms to the entire Spoke 4 address book. The questionnaire facilitated the identification, through participatory input, of an initial group of key stakeholders within the cultural heritage sector. This group served as the foundation for guiding the next three phases of the workshop. Figure 3 shows the number of stakeholders identified and shared by participants through the questionnaire.

FIGURE 3 PRELIMINAR PHASE RESULTS

4.3 Step 1 - Analysis and mapping of stakeholder interests and powers

Initially, participants received a reminder regarding the workshop's objectives, the process for stakeholder identification, and the planned session structure. This included an introduction to the working rooms, each dedicated to a quadrant of the helix and overseen by an experienced moderator.

Figure 4 presents the distribution of participants in the various rooms, and Table 1 shows the names of the participants distributed in the working rooms.

FIGURE 4 STAKEHOLDER MAPPING - DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS

Government	Industry	Civil Society	Academia
Montaldo S.	Damiano R.	Amitrano C.	Cilli C.
Benvenuti G.	Mariniello N.	Ferraris E.	Bertini M.
Pennacini C.	Santacroce M.	Casero C.	Pescarin S.
Corriero M.	Bagnaresi D.	Federici F.	Massaro S.
Genovese G.	Fanini B.	Barione A.	Thun Hohenstein U.
		Albano V.	Peroni S.
		Obisso S.	

TABLE 1 PHASE 1 - PARTICIPANTS DISTRIBUTION

Moderators were tasked with overseeing the discussion and operating on the MIRO platform, which was shown to participants in screen sharing.

FIGURE 5 GOOGLEMEET - INDUSTRY ROOM - CO-DESIGN ACTIVITY ON MIRO

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This phase consisted in assessing the interests, influence and potential impact of each stakeholder in Spoke 4 activities, starting with those identified through the census conducted on GoogleModules. Participants carried out three exercises, organized into three sets of questions.

The questions they answered were as follows:

1. **Interest analysis:** what are the main interests of the stakeholders identified in Cultural Heritage? How do interests differ among different stakeholder groups? Are there common goals among stakeholders or are there conflicts of interest?

FIGURE 6 INTEREST ANALYSIS OF GOVERNMENT STAKEHOLDERS

2. **influence analysis:** what is the level of influence or power of each stakeholder in the context of Cultural Heritage? What resources or capabilities can stakeholders offer to support Spoke 4 activities/projects?

FIGURE 7 INFLUENCE ANALYSIS OF INDUSTRY STAKEHOLDERS

3. **Analysis of potential impacts:** how could the activities related to cultural heritage and the CHANGES project positively affect the identified stakeholders? Are there potential negative impacts that could arise? What are stakeholders' main concerns about the impacts of cultural initiatives?

FIGURE 8 ANALYSIS OF POTENTIAL IMPACTS OF STAKEHOLDER INDUSTRY

The responses to the questions enabled the creation of the interest and influence map for each stakeholder, at this stage of the workshop, and to arrive at a selection on which to discuss in plenary during the second stage.

FIGURE 9 MAPPING OF INTEREST AND INFLUENCE OF CIVIL SOCIETY STAKEHOLDERS

4.4 Step 2 - Analysis of the degree of information on Spoke 4 activities

After the activity in the rooms were concluded, the moderators shared the results obtained in each room during a plenary session to integrate the findings with the input from all participants. Next, the analysis activity for phase 2 was presented: participants, starting from the matrices constructed in the individual rooms and reasoning from the perspective of a

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single helix segment, were guided by the moderators to analyse and provide a specific assessment of the degree of information of the surveyed stakeholders, as shown in Figure 10.

Stakeholders were clustered into three colour codes corresponding to:

- uninformed (brown);
- partially informed (purple);
- fully informed (blue).

FIGURE 10 STAKEHOLDER CLUSTERING BY DEGREE OF INFORMATION STAKEHOLDER CLUSTERING BY DEGREE OF INFORMATION

The analysis of the degree of stakeholder information allowed a second division into “internal stakeholders” (participating in the project and active in its development) and “external stakeholders” (potentially affected by the project even if not fully participating in its development).

FIGURE 11 RADAR MODEL USED IN CARRYING OUT PHASE 2

4.5 Step 3 - Discussion and identification of an engagement strategy

The final phase focused on identifying ad hoc engagement strategies for each stakeholder. The engagement tools and techniques envisioned by the project were shared, and participants were asked to associate the models they felt were most effective for each stakeholder. They selected these models from the following groups:

Social	Dissemination	Public events	Training events	Feedback
YouTube	Newsletter	Presentations	Summer school	Focus group
Instagram	E-mail	Deliverables	Online courses	Online pools
LinkedIn	Sector journal publications	Online exhibition	Webinar	Survey
	Press releases	Remote meetings	Conferences	Direct reports
	Web portals	In-person meetings		

TABLE 2 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

During the discussion, participants were given the opportunity to supplement TABLE 2 with additional suggestions to enrich the engagement strategy.

As part of Phase 3, participants were asked to consider the level of engagement not just for individual stakeholder, but for the group of stakeholders identified in the specific segments of interest and power.

5. Workshop outcomes

This section summarises the outcomes of discussions on engagement strategies in relation to specific segments of the quadruple helix.

5.1 Government

Starting from the mapping conducted during the preliminary phase, 14 stakeholders were identified for the Government section. During the discussion, the number and types of stakeholders were expanded to include the following:

GOVERNMENT

- **Municipalities where Spoke 4 use cases are developed**
- **Associazione Nazionale Comuni italiani (ANCI)**
- **Comune di Galtelli (NU)**
- **Comune di Aliano (MT)**
- **Comune di Torino**
- **Regione Piemonte**
- **Regione Toscana**
- **Direzione Generale Musei (MIC)**
- **Associazione Parchi Letterari**
- **Aziende di promozione turistica della Regione Basilicata**
- **Digital Library**
- **Fondazioni culturali**
- **Associazione Nazionale Musei Scientifici (ANMS)**
- **Associazioni museali (AMACI, ICOM)**
- **Museo Egizio di Torino**
- **Museo Galileo**
- **Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane (CRUI)**
- **Uffici scolastici regionali**
- **UNICEF**

TABLE 3 GOVERNMENT STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION

5.1.1 Stakeholder issue-mapping

Stakeholder analysis in the Government sector revealed a multiplicity of interests and objectives that reflect the complexity and multidimensionality of the public environment. Government stakeholders place **great importance on tourism and land promotion**, seeing tourism potential as a key driver for local and regional economic development. At the same time, a **strong interest is emerging in the protection and enhancement of natural and urban landscapes**, which are considered an integral part of cultural heritage.

Environmental sustainability is another priority issue. Stakeholders promote sustainable practices to ensure the preservation of the environment and the reduction of the ecological impact of human activities. This effort is intertwined with accessible and inclusive cultural promotion, which aims to make culture accessible to all, with initiatives that promote the inclusion of different segments of the population, including those who are marginalized.

Social inclusion is a key aspect, with stakeholders committed to using cultural programs to engage diverse communities. This is also reflected in the promotion of local and widespread museality, which values museums as tools for education and preservation of historical memory, and in the revival of local identity, with projects that recover and enhance the history of small towns and local communities.

The promotion of territorial identity is key to strengthening the sense of belonging and identity through targeted cultural initiatives. In addition, government stakeholders focus on sustainable development of regions and natural parks by encouraging balanced management of natural and cultural resources.

The use of advanced technologies to increase the visibility and enjoyment of cultural heritage is another relevant interest. This innovative approach is particularly supported by culture departments in large cities, which focus on broad cultural initiatives, and by mayors of smaller municipalities, which promote local initiatives.

Despite the variety of interests, Government sector stakeholders share common goals, with few differences highlighted. Some place greater emphasis on the economic sustainability of initiatives seeking to achieve effective results with limited resources. Others, however, focus primarily on advancing research and cultural development. The absence of a clear distinction of goals allowed for the evaluation of similar engagement strategies.

A positive aspect that emerged from the analysis is the **absence of significant conflicts of interest among stakeholders**, suggesting a strong potential for collaboration. Government stakeholders could express their willingness to contribute tangible resources to support Spoke 4 activities. They could support the activities by offering space for demonstrators and organizing events, thus facilitating the implementation of concrete and visible projects on the ground.

5.1.2 Identifying potential impacts

Government stakeholders can benefit significantly from participation in the project, particularly in terms of enhancing cultural heritage. This involvement can lead to increased visibility and attractiveness of the area, boosting tourism and, consequently, local economic development. Promoting cultural heritage through innovative and technologically advanced initiatives that reflect the specific activities of Spoke 4 can strengthen the local identity and sense of community belonging, creating a more cohesive and dynamic environment. Furthermore, collaboration between different public and private institutions can stimulate the sharing of knowledge and resources, improving the effectiveness of cultural and environmental policies.

However, some concerns about potential negative impacts of cultural initiatives emerge from the analysis. These include the overuse of digital platforms, which could penalize the on-site enjoyment of cultural heritage. This risk is particularly significant in contexts where direct, tangible experience is considered irreplaceable.

Another significant concern relates to the sustainability of the adopted solutions and their maintenance over time. Stakeholders are concerned that without adequate maintenance plans, cultural and technological infrastructure may deteriorate rapidly, undermining initial investments and reducing the effectiveness of initiatives. Maintenance costs are an additional concern, especially in settings where financial resources are limited.

5.1.3 Stakeholder influence and information mapping

In the mapping phase, participants opted for a clustering of stakeholders. The outcome of the discussion is summarized in the following table:

GOVERNMENT		INFLUENCE AND INTEREST RATE			
		HIGH INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	HIGH INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST
INFORMATION RATE	FULLY INFORMED	Municipalities where Spoke 4 use cases are located.	Assessorato alla Cultura e al Turismo, Regione Piemonte	Cultural foundations	Uffici scolastici regionali
				Associazione Parchi letterari	
	PARTIALLY INFORMED	Direzione Generale Musei del Ministero	Regioni	Digital Library	Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane (CRUI)
		Aziende di promozione turistica della Regione Basilicata.			
	NOT INFORMED	Associazione Nazionale Musei Scientifici (ANMS)			Associazione Nazionale Comuni italiani (ANCI)
		Associazioni museali (AMACI, ICOM)			UNICEF

TABLE 4 GOVERNMENT STAKEHOLDER INFLUENCE MAP

This analysis revealed a balanced distribution of stakeholders across quadrants, delineating a diverse landscape of project-related influences and interests.

In detail, a balanced situation is observed between the number of stakeholders placed in the "high influence, high interest", "low influence, high interest" and "low influence, low interest" quadrants. This suggests that many stakeholders are deeply interested in the project, although their degree of influence varies widely. Only two stakeholders are in the "high influence, low

interest" quadrant: most influential stakeholders therefore also appear to be interested in the proposed initiatives.

Based on the level of information, there are, as might be expected, differences even within the same quadrant (high influence, high interest). This information gap can impact the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement. Well-informed stakeholders can actively participate and make more substantial and targeted contributions, while less informed ones may not take full advantage of opportunities for involvement or may misinterpret project goals and actions.

In summary, the balance of high and low-influence stakeholders, combined with their varied level of interest, indicates a complex but potentially very fertile environment for project outcomes. However, the information gap that emerged represents a crucial challenge to be addressed. The engagement and communication strategy for key stakeholders in the Government segment will need to consider these elements to close the information gap with appropriate engagement tools prior to strategic engagement.

5.2 Industry

Starting from the mapping activity conducted during the preliminary phase, 11 stakeholders were identified for the Industry section:

INDUSTRY
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Engineering• DATABENC• Dotit• 4Science• ETT• Consorzio cultura e innovazione• RE:LAB s.r.l.• Brixel• QAcademy• Alicubi• StrategiX s.r.l.

TABLE 5 INDUSTRY STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION

5.2.1 Stakeholder issue-mapping

Stakeholders belonging to this sector show interests in key issues such as innovation, technological advancement, cultural promotion, partnership formation, consortia building, and participation in calls and collaborative networks. This shared interest in the development and integration of new technologies and collaborative strategies is a unifying element that can facilitate cooperation among different stakeholders in the sector.

However, these common interests can potentially be discordant when getting into the details of individual stakeholder actions and activities. The socioeconomic and not just geographic diversity of the territories in which they operate, the types of assets and collections with which each relates, and any commitment to specific technologies, can create significant differences in how they operate. In addition, the distinction between horizontal and vertical working approaches, as well as variation in interests based on company size, can influence the dynamics of collaboration. For example, while a large entity might have resources for a broad spectrum of activities, a small stakeholder might offer more focused but equally crucial specializations.

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Despite these differences, no conflicts of interest emerged among the identified stakeholders. On the contrary, the analysis revealed the presence of common goals: this consensus on overall objectives facilitates the construction of a cooperative and productive environment, where each stakeholder can contribute his or her specific resources and expertise.

5.2.2 Identifying potential impacts

The conducted analysis revealed different ways in which industry stakeholders interrelate with Spoke 4 activities. Even small stakeholders, often underestimated, can be strategic for specific activities due to their specialization, which can become a competitive advantage, enabling the implementation of innovative and customized solutions that large entities may not be able to develop as efficiently.

Stakeholders with a higher level of influence, on the other hand, could act as policy makers, influencing cultural policies at a broader level. This influence can be instrumental in directing needed resources and attention to cultural heritage projects, ensuring significant and lasting impact. Their ability to shape cultural policies can facilitate the creation of a more favourable regulatory and financial framework, promoting the sustainability and growth of cultural initiatives.

In summary, stakeholder diversity, if well managed, can be a valuable resource for optimal dissemination of Spoke 4 activities. The combination of technical expertise, strategic resources, and capacity for political influence creates a dynamic and potentially highly effective collaborative ecosystem. This synergy between different actors in the cultural heritage sector is fundamental for developing innovative solutions, promoting sustainability, and ensuring a lasting positive impact on local communities and the cultural heritage itself.

At the same time, there are numerous activities that could benefit stakeholders involved in the project, including: (i) enhancement of cultural assets; (ii) improvement of technologies; (iii) propensity for innovation; (iv) interaction with users; (v) diversification; involvement of communities in project activities; (vi) knowledge of tools developed by the project; (vii) advantage over knowledge; (viii) knowledge of trends; (ix) and Research.

Industry stakeholders could also benefit from project activities by gaining priority access to new frameworks, emerging open-source technologies, and insights from other companies, positioning themselves as early adopters of technological advancements.

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Possible concerns of Industry stakeholders could include: (i) investment costs; (ii) lack of visibility of activities and involvement of companies; (iii) lack of appropriate expertise; (iv) continuity of the project and the collaborative relationship; (v) infrastructure; (vi) political risks; (vii) technological risks; (viii) and the relationship with the local area.

Few appear to be potentially perceived negative impacts, such as technology lock-ins, the problem associated with proprietary solutions, lack of interoperability, and potentially non-compatible formats. All of which will need to be handled as part of the planning of specific collaborations.

5.2.3 Stakeholder influence and information mapping

The analysis of the interests and level of information among these stakeholders was promising, with the majority being well-informed or moderately informed and all showing strong interest in the project activities. Their participation could lead to several benefits, including: expanded availability of spaces for demonstrations, development of new cultural policies, enhanced specialization, and increased technological capabilities. The following table shows the analysis of the level of influence and interest and the level of information of the stakeholders.

INDUSTRY		INFLUENCE AND INTEREST RATE			
		HIGH INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	HIGH INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST
INFORMATION RATE	FULLY INFORMED	Engineering			
		DATABENC (Distretto ad Alta Tecnologia per i BENi Culturali)			
		TICHE			
		ETT			
		Consorzio cultura e innovazione			RE:LAB
	PARTIALLY INFORMED			Brixel	
				QAcademy	
				Alicubi	
	NOT INFORMED				

TABLE 6 INDUSTRY STAKEHOLDER INFLUENCE MAP

5.3 Academy

Starting from the mapping phase conducted during the preliminary phase, 10 stakeholders were identified for the Academia section. In the discussion stages, the number and variety of stakeholders were expanded. The following table shows the stakeholders analysed:

ACADEMIA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniss • POLIMI • POLITO • Bocconi • DHFACTORY RomaTre • CNR IMATI • CNR ISPC • UNIBAS (Università degli Studi della Basilicata) • UNIBA (Università degli Studi di Bari) • UNICA (Università degli Studi di Cagliari) • Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università italiane (CRUI) • Consorzio Matera HUB • Istituto Arte e Restauro di Firenze • ICCD • Fondazione Scuola BB.CC. • Dipartimento scienze storiche dell'Università di Siena • Gipsoteca di Arte Antica dell'Università di Pisa (GIARA) • UNIOR • UnaEuropa • Università afferenti a CHANGES

TABLE 7 ACADEMIA STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION

5.3.1 Stakeholder issue-mapping

The preliminary phase focused on identifying the interests of stakeholders in the Academy segment was highly productive. Participants' deep understanding of these stakeholders enabled them to explore the diverse interests within the Cultural Heritage sector in greater detail. The analysis revealed several key interests in the approach to cultural heritage. First, there is a strong interest in heritage enhancement, which goes beyond mere physical preservation and embraces its interpretation and communication to the public. This indicates a desire to preserve and promote cultural wealth in all its forms.

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Scientific research has a central role, reflecting the importance of deepening the understanding of cultural heritage through multidisciplinary studies ranging from archaeology to art history, from science to sociology. "Third Mission" represents an engagement of cultural institutions in contributing to the social and economic development of communities through public engagement initiatives, training and interdisciplinary collaboration. Another area of interest is teacher training to integrate cultural heritage into education, promoting greater awareness of cultural roots from an early age.

Heritage management requires organizational strategies and practices to effectively and sustainably manage cultural heritage, which include aspects of preservation, financing, and operational management. Public engagement is essential to actively involve the public in the cultural heritage enhancement and management process by encouraging participation, dialogue and interaction with cultural institutions. Territorial promotion and tourism enhancement exploit cultural heritage as a resource for local economic development through marketing initiatives, cultural tourism and enhancement of territorial identities.

Approaches such as *Citizen science* and *Citizen engagement* involve citizens in scientific data collection or decision making, thus contributing to cultural heritage research and preservation. The use of digital tools and packages to visit museums aims to improve accessibility, experience and enjoyment of cultural heritage, both within institutions and through online platforms or mobile applications.

Finally, management policy formation and new professional development reflect the need to address contemporary challenges in cultural heritage management, including legal, ethical, technological, and management aspects.

The analysis identified both convergences of goals, such as research, education, and impact on the local area, and some conflicts of interest, such as those between the research and museum fields. These conflicts can be addressed through strategies of collaboration, dialogue and participatory governance that consider the different perspectives and interests of the stakeholders involved.

5.3.2 Identifying potential impacts

Stakeholders identified for this segment could benefit from Spoke 4 activity on multiple levels, including enhanced visibility of Heritage, development of new research methodologies,

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improved accessibility, social inclusion, and increased and broadened and diversified audience. Potential benefits also encompass economic impact, development and adoption of new open-access tools for enterprises, influence on new generations; enhanced stakeholder visibility, increased user participation and satisfaction, bolstered social impact, and heightened online visitation rates.

Against these benefits, a few disadvantages emerged, including issues related to data storage, maintenance of data and storage devices, personnel management, shortage of specialists, and investment costs.

There were also few concerns, primarily related to compliance with cultural heritage regulations, which could impose limits on issued such as the reproduction and dissemination of images. Additionally, concerns included the potential for precarious staffing and expertise, as well as the maintenance and management of technological infrastructure.

5.3.3 Stakeholder influence and information mapping

Despite the large number of stakeholders identified in the preliminary stages of the workshop for this quadrant of the helix, the mapping activity for engagement included clustering and eliminating some stakeholders. During the discussion, has emerged a desire to focus on the most strategic stakeholders who were not already part of the project activities. This approach ensures that the concluding scheme maintains strategic coherence with the other segments of the quadruple helix analysed.

The following table shows the results of the analysis of the level of influence and interest, as well as the level of stakeholder information:

ACADEMIA		INFLUENCE AND INTEREST RATE			
		HIGH INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	HIGH INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST
INFORMATION RATE	FULLY INFORMED	Fondazione CHANGES	Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università italiane (CRUI)	CNR	
				Universities affiliated with Spoke 4	
	PARTIALLY INFORMED	Fondazione Scuola BB.CC.			
	NOT INFORMED				Consorzio Matera HUB
				UnaEuropa	

TABLE 8 ACADEMIA STAKEHOLDER INFLUENCE MAP

The high degree of information and level of interest shown by most stakeholders in the matrix indicate an already significant engagement in the project by this key stakeholder category. This is a crucial element in ensuring effective collaboration and the optimal realization of project objectives.

Among these stakeholders, those identified as fully informed and with high influence - specifically those belonging to the CHANGES Foundation stakeholder network - could play a key role in providing expert advice and guiding the implementation of advanced solutions. These solutions would be functional in engaging other stakeholders from Academia or Government.

The expertise of these stakeholders is a key resource for tackling complex challenges and adopting innovative approaches. The opportunity for training and staffing can ensure that the project has access to the specialized expertise and skilled human resources needed for its implementation.

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In addition, concerted use cases with stakeholders can offer valuable practical perspectives and insights into real needs in the field, thereby helping to guide project development more efficiently. The reported new methodologies and technologies could be crucial for innovation and progress in the field of cultural heritage, enabling the project to remain at the forefront and achieve remarkable results.

Overall, the elevated level of interest, the expertise of participants, and the resources identified are very promising for the projects' success. However, it is important to develop specific and differentiated engagement strategies for less informed stakeholders with a low level of interest and influence.

5.4 Civil Society

Starting from the mapping conducted during the preliminary phase, 10 stakeholders were identified for the Civil Society section. During the discussion stages, the number and type of stakeholders were expanded. The following table shows the analysed stakeholders:

CIVIL SOCIETY
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associazione per l'informatica umanistica e la cultura digitale (AIUCD) • Associazione categoria industria videogiochi (IIDEA) • Associazione IVIPRO • Associazione italiana editori (AIE) • Associazione Scienze Umane e Sociali (SISUS) • Fondazione Piemonte dal vivo • Fondazione di Sardegna • Coro Voches e Amentos • Associazione musei Arte Contemporanea italiani (AMACI) • Territorio di Galtellì (NU) (biblioteca, guide turistiche, proloco, agriturismi...) • Territorio di Aliano (Artisti...) • Fondazione Cassa risparmio • Fondazione Cariparma • Fondazione Monte parma • Fondazione Torino musei • Fondazione Cariplo • Fondazione compagnia San Paolo • (Cluster) Biblioteche, Archivi, Musei...

TABLE 9 CIVIL SOCIETY STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION

5.4.1 Stakeholder-issue mapping

Civil society, represented by a broad spectrum of actors, organizations, and communities, plays a key role in Cultural Heritage (BB.CC.). These actors operate outside of governments and the private sector, aiming to promote social, cultural and economic well-being through active participation and involvement in civic and cultural life. The discussion revealed that the impact of civil society in the BB.CC. sector is significant and diverse. Indeed, these actors play a crucial role in promoting awareness and appreciation of cultural heritage, protecting and preserving cultural property, promoting cultural diversity, and disseminating knowledge.

Moreover, civil society contributes to innovation in the sector by promoting new ideas, practices, and approaches to the appreciation and enjoyment of cultural heritage. It often acts

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as a catalyst for change, encouraging collaboration between different actors and the search for creative and sustainable solutions to the challenges the sector faces.

Civil society participation in the BB.CC. sector manifests itself through a range of activities, from raising public awareness and promoting local cultural initiatives, to advocating for cultural rights and mobilizing to safeguard threatened cultural sites and traditions.

In the same way, it is important to emphasize how civil society can engage the broader public to build best practices and guide research and development of the Cultural Heritage sector. Adopting innovative strategies to attract and engage the public is essential to maintain attention and interest in heritage and land. This may include the use of immersive technologies, the creation of interactive exhibition spaces, and the cultural promotion of the area to stimulate public participation, with a focus on raising awareness among younger people. Another area of interest concerns investments in territories aimed at supporting the cultural and economic development of local communities. This translates into a search for new funding opportunities, for example through calls promoted by universities or through partnerships with banking foundations. The goal is to promote the enhancement of local cultural heritage and create new opportunities for economic and social growth.

The transition to digital is another key aspect of interests in the BB.CC. sector. This involves the digitization of cultural materials and the adoption of new technologies to enhance the enjoyment and promotion of cultural heritage online. The objective is to ensure broader and more inclusive access to cultural heritage, reaching new audiences and providing more engaging and interactive experiences.

Finally, there is a strong interest in the promotion and enhancement of the local area, which is evident through initiatives aimed at promoting awareness of the area and enriching its cultural identity. This can be done through the creation of spaces for sharing, promotion of cultural events, and raising awareness in the local community about the importance of cultural heritage. Moreover, there is a growing awareness of the importance of actively involving the local community in the management and enhancement of its cultural heritage to ensure greater sustainability and better protection in the long run.

5.4.2 Identifying potential impacts

During the analysis, no disadvantages or concerns emerged regarding the potential involvement of these stakeholders. Instead, the focus was on the benefits that the project could bring to these stakeholders, particularly the positive spillover effects over time. However, there is a need to assess the impacts and spillover effects of project activities on particularly influential stakeholders, such as banking foundations. This assessment will guide a dissemination and involvement strategy that aligns with their expectations.

5.4.3 Stakeholder influence and information mapping

The following table shows the results on the analysis of the level of influence and interest and the level of stakeholder information:

CIVIL SOCIETY		INFLUENCE AND INTEREST RATE			
		HIGH INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	HIGH INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, HIGH INTEREST	LOW INFLUENCE, LOW INTEREST
INFORMATION RATE	FULLY INFORMED	Territorio di Aliano		Associazione UCIM	
				Territorio di Galtelli	
	PARTIALLY INFORMED	Biblioteche, Archivi, Musei, Gallerie			
	NOT INFORMED	Fondazioni bancarie			Fondazione di Sardegna
					Fondazione Piemonte dal vivo
					Associazione categoria videoludica (IIDEA)

TABLE 10 CIVIL SOCIETY STAKEHOLDER INFLUENCE MAP

As evident, there are different types of strategic stakeholders distinguished by their impact and influence. However, a significant initial challenge for engagement activities is the varying levels of stakeholder information. The presence of strategic stakeholders with limited or no information necessitates a targeted strategy to maximize the project's potential and extend its benefits to broader segments of civil society.

During discussions, it became clear that the most influential banking foundations are those active in regions where cultural heritage enhancement is most prominent, highlighting their keen interest in the sector.

6. Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

After mapping the stakeholders and creating matrices for their levels of interest, influence, and information, the analysis focused on stakeholder engagement, considering two key elements: the pyramid of engagement levels and strategies provided by the CHANGES project.

FIGURE 12 LEVELS OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

In Figure 12 are reported levels considered when creating specific strategies.

The "Collaboration" level should be utilized for stakeholders who exhibit high interest and influence on the project. These stakeholders are considered potential providers of crucial information, authorizations and resources.

The "Involvement" level should be utilized for stakeholders who possess high influence but may have limited interest or resources to actively participate in the project. Despite this, their contribution can be crucial to the success of the project. In this case, it is important to initiate specific efforts to involve this group early in the project to maximize their involvement and input.

The engagement strategy built on the "Consultation" level should include stakeholders who show high interest in the project but have low decision-making influence. While they can offer support to the project, their ability to influence outcomes may be limited. However, involving them in the decision-making process can be helpful in obtaining valuable feedback and creating an environment of collaboration and participation.

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The "Information" level should be employed for stakeholders who have limited interest or involvement in project results. Generally, it is not necessary to allocate significant resources to their active involvement. However, keeping these stakeholders informed about project activities is important to ensure transparency and accountability for decisions made.

The following is a graphic summary that takes these elements into consideration:

INFLUENCE	HIGH	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE
	LOW	INFORM	CONSULT
STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY		LOW	HIGH
		INTEREST	

FIGURE 13 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY (INFLUENCE, INTEREST)

Based on the positioning of each stakeholder in the interest and influence matrices, it is crucial to adopt specific strategies that consider the different levels of involvement. A set of engagement tools was proposed to the workshop participants to enable the structuring of a strategy aligned with the project's dissemination and communication activities.

The specific engagement strategies presented are listed below:

Social

- Youtube
- Instagram
- LinkedIn

Dissemination

- Newsletter
- Scientific publications and journals
- Press releases
- Official emails
- Web portal

Outreach events

- Presentations
- Periodic reporting (deliverable)
- Online exhibition
- Remote meetings
- In-person meetings

Training events

- Summer school
- Online courses
- Webinar
- Conferences

Feedback

- Focus Group
- Online polls
- Survey
- Direct reports

Other noted during discussions

- Spoke videogame
- Participation in industry fairs
- Virtual tutorial

FIGURE 14 SPECIFIC ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

The assignment of these specific strategies within the individual segments of the quadruple helix took into account the specific nature of the tool. For example, in engagement through social media such as YouTube, Instagram and LinkedIn, the level of collaboration could be the partnerships for specific projects or the organization of joint events. Indeed, dedicated groups or pages could be created on these social media to collaborate on joint initiatives or to promote shared projects. At the same time, social media can also provide an informational tool for civil society and the public about the initiatives promoted by the Spoke. Differences in the target audience of the social segment were also considered: Instagram is a broader engagement tool on the citizenry, while LinkedIn by its nature represents a professional target audience for the business sector as well.

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As for engagement tools such as webinars and focus groups, they allow for a level of active user engagement, with the ability to interact directly, ask questions and provide detailed feedback. These tools are effective in engaging users in in-depth discussions and gathering opinions and suggestions.

Newsletters and presentations can be considered engagement tools at the consultation level, as they provide regular information and updates to users, allowing them to stay informed about project activities and give feedback through specific channels.

In contrast, tools such as press releases, scientific publications, and online courses tend to represent a more informational level of engagement, where information is disseminated unidirectionally to users without necessarily engaging them in active dialogue. These tools are useful for providing in-depth information and education, but they may not encourage direct user involvement.

6.3 Government engagement strategy plan

During the discussion on the Government segment, emerged a recognised need to devise a strategy to enhance the engagement of stakeholders who have significant interest and influence and are already informed. Specifically, the importance of establishing direct connections with industry stakeholders who are already well informed of the Spoke's activities was highlighted, along with the suggestion of organizing face-to-face meetings to support initiatives. Moreover, it was proposed to prioritise consultative engagement to better align communication with stakeholders' policy requirements, thereby mitigating the risk of disengagement.

On the other hand, a more direct and customised strategy could be adopted for stakeholders with significant influence but limited interest or resources. To increase their involvement, the strategy should take into account the characteristics of the area and specific needs to invite these stakeholders to sessions or inaugurations (e.g., inaugurations of the demonstrators identified with the case-core) consistent with their mission. This could include inviting them to participate in targeted focus groups to gather detailed feedback on the proposed initiatives.

For stakeholders with marginal interest or limited influence, such as regional school offices, it might be useful to adopt an outreach strategy through training initiatives, which is a crucial element of their goals.

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A combined approach that integrates collaborative, engaging, and informative strategies can help maximize institutional stakeholder engagement and encourage more active participation by all stakeholders with greater influence.

6.4 Industry engagement strategy plan

In the Industry segment discussion, the emphasis was on the pivotal role of industry trade shows as primary engagement tools to promote information dissemination and foster active participation among industry players. These events offer a valuable platform to deliver updates on cutting-edge developments and generate interest in Spoke initiatives. Moreover, a consultative approach through focus groups was suggested, especially for those stakeholders with high influence but low interest in project initiatives. This would allow for a more detailed assessment of potential specific impacts and the active involvement of stakeholders in the analysis and definition of future strategies.

For stakeholders with marginal interest or limited influence, information and training strategies were identified as the most effective. The use of social media such as YouTube could be a valuable channel for disseminating online tutorials and scientific papers, constantly updating industry stakeholders on the latest news and developments in the BB.CC sector.

Emerging for this segment is the importance of adopting a broader and more nuanced range of strategies, carefully considering the degree of stakeholder information and broadening the audience through active participation in industry trade shows and specific demonstrators. This focused approach can help maximize engagement and foster more productive and synergistic collaboration between the Spoke project and Industry.

6.5 Academia engagement strategy plan

In the discussion of the Academia segment, emerged the need to promote a strategy that can improve the degree of collaboration with stakeholders characterised by significant interest and influence who are already partially or fully informed. This could translate into the creation of focused tutorials on specific BB.CC. related topics, active participation on platforms such as LinkedIn by identifying the specific sector target audience and sharing informative and valuable content on YouTube. Moreover, participation in industry fairs, such as Turisma or Digital Heritage 2025, could provide opportunities for networking and knowledge exchange with other industry players by expanding the engagement strategy of identified stakeholders.

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For stakeholders with major influence but limited interest or resources, such as some interest groups or less active institutions, a more direct and personalized engagement strategy is suggested, which could include participating in specific focus groups to gather detailed feedback and creating virtual online exhibitions to engage stakeholders in an interactive and engaging way. In addition, publishing scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals could be an effective way to reach this interest group and share specialized knowledge.

Finally, for stakeholders with limited interest or marginal influence, such as the public or stakeholders outside the specific sector, an information and awareness-raising strategy is suggested. This could include making ad hoc presentations on cultural issues of public interest, which can be shared through online and offline channels to reach a wider audience and promote awareness on BB.CC issues.

In summary, employing collaborative, engaging, and informative approaches can enhance stakeholder engagement in the BB.CC. sector, ensuring the success of cultural and heritage initiatives overall.

6.6 Civil Society engagement strategy plan

The unique attributes of the Civil Society quadrant, along with significant variations in information levels and engagement sizes, have prompted discussions on adopting a strategy incorporating modern and interactive tools. For instance, leveraging social media platforms like Instagram could effectively engage a younger and more dynamic audience through visual and interactive content addressing BB.CC issues.

Introducing smartphone video games could represent an innovative approach to engaging stakeholders and raising awareness about cultural and heritage issues in an interactive way, particularly targeting the younger generation and those interested in innovation and technology.

Regarding the specific engagement strategy with banking foundations, it is important to consider the nature of the stakeholders and their level of information. Since banking foundations may have a significant interest in the BB.CC. sector but may not be experts in the field or interested in all Spoke initiatives, a preliminary informative approach could be adopted. A first step could be to use tools such as openings (e.g., core-case demonstrators) with ad hoc invitations and digital exhibits to provide detailed information about the activities

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and goals of the project itself. This could include sharing educational materials, ad hoc presentations, and organizing events.

Following the informational and initial engagement phase, a more in-depth consultation phase may proceed with brainstorming sessions, bilateral meetings, or focus groups to explore collaboration opportunities and synergies between banking foundation and Spoke activities.

6.7 Conclusions

The methodology adopted and the outcomes of the workshop enabled an exploration of the intricate dynamics defining stakeholder engagement in Cultural Heritage (BB.CC.), particularly across sectors identified within the quadruple helix framework. Through a thorough analysis of the Government, Industry, Civil Society, and Academy segments, we identified a diverse range of interests and engagement strategies with a high degree of precision. This approach underscores the significance and varied contributions of each stakeholder within the BB.CC. landscape.

Various tools have been identified and cataloged to activate the appropriate level of engagement, ranging from trade fairs and participation in focus groups to the distribution of informational materials and creation of content on social media. These tools are summarized in the figure below:

FIGURE 1 SUMMARY OF STRATEGIES THAT EMERGED FROM THE "CULTUREINDIALOGUE" WORKSHOP.

It should be underlined that **a larger number of stakeholders were identified than the minimum KPIs expected from the WP5 deliverable**, to allow a broader range of opportunities in each area of interest.

Finally, it is important to highlight that some of the tools identified during the discussion were considered applicable across different Stakeholders. For instance, the newsletter was recognised as a tool that could enhance coordinated efforts across all segments of the quadruple helix. Another versatile tool is online exhibitions, which have the potential to engage tool even beyond the national levels that were the objects of analysis.

The guidelines articulated in this document, arising from collaborative efforts during the "Culture in Dialogue" workshop, will serve as the cornerstone for developing a focused and cohesive communication plan. This plan will be tailored to address emerging needs, considering the specifics of the context and the established objectives, to ensure the optimal and effective dissemination of the project's messages and results.